

ARRAY AND ARRAYS INSTALLATION

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ANNOTATION

This article provides the syntax for declaring arrays in JAVA programming language and declaring a multi-dimensional array. Objects to the array about issues given _ of the issues The solution is JAVA programming in the language coded .

Key words : array, length , literal

ANNOTATION

In this article, the syntax for declaring arrays and declaring a multi-dimensional array in the JAVA programming language is given. Issues related to array of objects are given. The solutions to the problems were coded in the JAVA programming language.

Keywords: array, length, literal

Everyone programming languages like JAV A arrays with to work powers up . of JAVA main from the goals one is this safety . That's why for C and C ++ languages encountered a lot problems are solved in JAVA done _ Har one to the pointer when he is silent automatic means null _ is given From application before you each one applicable pointer your initialization and to him meaning give need _

JAVA arrays announcement to do

```
int ab [ ] //
```

```
int [ ] al //
```

This is a record array himself not an array to the object to be sent makes _ Attention give , an array size not shown .

Simple ones array make up

```
int [ ] al = {1,2,3,4,5};
```

massive the length determination Arrays in JAVA length for for in advance determined style is used ;

at the index of the first element is 0. Of the array the most big massive element using length-1 determination can _ If you objects array creating if you are , always new key the word to use need _

Objects array .

Objects array how to compose the following in the example seeing we go out

```
public class Animal {  
    private int number of legs ;  
    Animal ( int number of legs) {  
        this . number of legs = number of legs;  
    }  
    Animal [ ] a = new Animal [ 20 ] ;  
    System. out printin (a length + « animal »);  
    for ( int i = 0; i < a. length; i + + )  
        a [ i ] = new Animal ( i % 2 + 1)* 2 ) ;  
}
```

Array initialization for also meanings the list apply can _ In this meanings circle to brackets is obtained (this without massive size compilation on time reflection meat)

```
integer [ ] a = {  
    new integer (1);  
    new integer (2);  
    new integer (3);  
};
```

A lot dimensional arrays

Also a lot sized arrays announcement to do can _

```
int [ ] [ ] a;  
int [ ] a [ ];
```

One sized as in array a lot sized the array announcement in doing meanings suddenly initialization can _

```
int [ ] [ ] a = {{ 1,2,3},{5,6}};
```

Or cycle inside program work on time initialization can _

String.

String variables make up for the String class objects is used . String of variables meaning quote into is taken . Literal in binding the first a String object in the attempt in memory is made .

new literal String object when added again is made . To new literals have is a String object is added .

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